

Informed Consent Agreement

Before taking part in this study, please read the following information and indicate below whether you consent to the conditions of participation.

As part of a research project focusing on **music recommender systems**, we would like to understand how recommendations are perceived by end users of such systems. Additionally, we want to identify how the transparency of these systems could be improved. For this purpose, we are asking you to contribute your perspective through participating in an experiment. Your input will be used to inform future research that aims to improve music recommendation. The experiment will take approximately **45-60 minutes**, and will be in the form of closed questions followed by a think aloud-task and an interview.

With your permission, we will make an **audio recording** during the study. Only the research team will have access to this recording and the recording will be destroyed after transcription. All documents and recordings are kept in secure locations approved by [University].

This study is carried out by [researchers] as part of their PhD projects, and is funded by the [University Department].

Participation is **completely voluntary**. You can decide to withdraw at any time and for any reason, including after participating. However, if you choose to withdraw after participating, we will not be required to undo the processing of your data that has taken place up until that time. The personal data we have obtained from you up until the time when you withdraw your consent will be erased (where personal data is any data that can be linked to you, so this excludes any already anonymized data).

We intend to report **the results of this survey** in publications and/or presentations. Upon request, we can share these results with you through email. We also intend to share collected survey data with the broader research community, following FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. Any information from the questionnaire or audio recording that could identify you as an individual will be replaced or removed before publishing the survey data. Personal characteristics are only collected in broad categories. Therefore, **your identity as a participant will remain confidential at all times**, and the risk of participation will be minimal. The data will be stored for 10 years.

This project adheres to the **ethical guidelines** established by the [University's Ethics Review Board], and falls under fundamental research without any commercial purpose nor external stakeholders or partners. If you have any complaints or questions about the processing of personal data, please send an email to the [Privacy Officer, email]. The Privacy Officer will also be able to assist you in exercising the rights you have under the GDPR. For details of our legal basis for using personal data and the rights you have over your data, please see the University's privacy information at [website].

For more information regarding this project, please contact:
[Researchers]

Agreement

- I am 18 years or older.
- I have read the information above and understand the nature and goal of this research project.
- I understand my participation is voluntary, and that I may withdraw from the study at any time.
- I understand that audio recordings will be made during the study.
- I understand that my responses may be shared with the broader research community and may be reported in scientific publications. Any information that could identify me as an individual will be replaced or removed.
- I agree to participate in the research project as described above.

[I Agree]